

Eclipse Soundscapes: Data Collector Submission

Introduction

1. What is your 5-digit zip code?

This might be different from the zip code where you completed the data collection. This information is shared with NASA Science Activation so that they can better understand where people are getting involved with the projects that they support.

If you do not know your zip code, or if you live outside of the United States, please enter 99999. *

Location

2. What is the location of your data collection? Please enter your location using your device's location or type in latitude and longitude in decimal degrees. (Example: 41.40338, 2.17403) *

Latitude

Longitude

3. Please select the option that describes your outside observation location: *

- Urban / City
- Suburban
- Rural / Countryside

4. Please select additional descriptions that describe your outside data collection location: Choose all that apply. *

- Park
- Forest
- Field or pasture
- Desert
- Beach
- Riverfront
- Lakefront
- Mountain area
- Hiking or Biking trail
- Zoo
- Farm

National Park, please specify:

National or State Forest, please specify:

Other, please specify:

5. Do you have additional information to share about your location? (For example, near a major road? Near a power generator or power supply station? Near particular animals/insects nesting/habitat? etc) Details and info always help!

6. Data Collection Start Time:

What time did you begin your data collection? Please include the hour and minute separated by a colon (HH:MM format), using a 24-hour clock. Valid examples include 08:32 and 20:09. *

Please select your time zone: *

Eastern Time Zone
Central Time Zone
Mountain Time Zone
Pacific Time Zone
Alaska Time Zone
Hawaii-Aleutian Time Zone

7. Data Collection Stop Time:

What time did you stop your data collection? Please include the hour and minute separated by a colon (HH:MM format), using a 24-hour clock. Valid examples include 08:32 and 20:09. *

Please select your time zone: *

Eastern Time Zone
Central Time Zone
Mountain Time Zone
Pacific Time Zone
Alaska Time Zone
Hawaii-Aleutian Time Zone

8. What is your AudioMoth's 3 digit ES ID#? *

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9. When will you mail your MicroSD Card?

Use this format - MM/DD/YYYY *

10. Please provide your email address so we can check in with you on the MicroSD mailing and then email you a Data Collector Certificate. *

14. ***BEFORE*** being an Eclipse Soundscapes Data Collector, which of the following senses did you think you should use to make scientific observations? Choose all that apply. *

- Eyes / Sight
- Ears / Sound
- Touch/Feel
- Nose/Smell
- Tongue/Taste

15. Now, ***AFTER*** being an Eclipse Soundscapes Data Collector, which of the following senses do you think you should use to make scientific observations? Choose all that apply. *

- Eyes / Sight
- Ears / Sound
- Touch / Feel
- Nose / Smell
- Tongue / Taste

Experience Feedback

16. What was the most interesting thing that you learned during the last training or activity that you completed?

17. Do you have any comments about the last training or activity, or about the Eclipse Soundscapes Project in general, that you'd like to share?

18. Do you plan to continue participating in the ES Project? *

- Yes
- Maybe
- No, please explain:

19. The evaluation team would like to interview some ES Project participants to learn more about their experiences. Do we have your permission to contact you in the future to request an interview? *

- Yes
- No, thank you

20. Thank you for your willingness to participate in an interview. If you are selected for this opportunity, the evaluators will contact you via email to schedule the interview. Please provide your email address.

21. How did you complete this Eclipse Soundscapes training or activity? *

Self-paced online lessons

In-person learning event (please specify location):

Webinar learning event (please specify when / by whom):

22. What is your age? *

13-17

18-24

25-34

35-44

45-54

55-64

65 and over

Prefer not to say

23. Please specify your ethnicity. Select all that apply. *

- African-American or Black
- Asian or Asian American
- Caucasian or White (non-Hispanic)
- Latinx or Hispanic
- Native American or Alaska Native
- Native Hawaiian or Pacific Islander
- Prefer to self-identify:
- Prefer not to say

24. How would you describe your gender? *

- Female
- Male
- Non-binary/non-conforming
- Prefer to self-describe:
- Prefer not to answer

25. The concept of disability used to imply an impairment of a person. In 2011, the World Health Organization redefined disability as a mismatch between the person and the environment they are in. Indeed, the social model of disability, which many members of the disability community identify with, states that it is not the person who is disabled, but the environment that disables them.

Do you have any long-term or chronic conditions that may impact your ability to move easily, see, hear, or speak, or to learn, remember, or concentrate or require ongoing accommodation? Please select all that apply. *

- No.
- Yes, Mobility: Difficulty walking, or walking for extended periods of time.
- Yes, Visual: Blindness, low vision, forms of color-blindness.
- Yes, Hearing: Deafness, hearing loss, severe tinnitus.
- Yes, Motor: Limited fine or gross motor control, e.g., tremors due to Parkinson's disease.
- Yes, Mental health conditions: Including depression, anxiety, post-traumatic stress disorder, etc.
- Yes, Chronic illness: Various diagnoses; may involve chronic pain, fatigue, or other symptoms.
- Yes, Self Identify:
- Prefer not to answer